

Design and Analysis of Airborne Antenna Positioning Mechanism using CAD and FEA Tools

Mahesh L¹, Divyesh Piyush Sinha², D Bhavik Chakravarthy³, Arush Shashikanth Chappannamath³, Ajai Kumar Shrivastava⁴, Rameshkumar S C⁵

^{1,5} Associate Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, India

² Student, Department of Mechatronics Engineering, REVA University, India

³ Student, Department of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, India

⁴ Scientist 'F', LRDE, DRDO, India

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the combination of Computer-Aided Design (CAD) and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) techniques to improve the efficiency and performance of the Airborne Antenna Positioning Mechanism. The goal of this work is to use fundamental sophisticated simulation techniques to address crucial difficulties in the design and optimization of an antenna positioning mechanism. This strategy will make use of modern R&D techniques such as CAD software and simulation tools, allowing for the creation of efficient solutions. The results section presents findings obtained from CAD and FEA simulations, including improvements in radar's mechanical performance for achieving a better Field of View in a fighter jet radar system enhancing situational awareness, detection range, target tracking, weapon engagement, and also leading to blind spot reduction as it improves navigation and terrain.

Keywords: Airborne Radar, Blind Spot, CAD, FEA, Wedge Mechanism.

1. Introduction

An outline of radar technology is given in this introduction, along with explanations of its types, applications, advantages, components, materials, and operating principles. A key tool in remote sensing, radar is an acronym for Radio Detection and Ranging. It uses electromagnetic waves to find, identify, and track objects in the atmosphere. Radar is an object detection system that utilizes radio waves. It sends out radio waves and listens for the bounce back to determine how far away and fast objects are moving, which enables to see through darkness, fog, and clouds, making it useful for airplanes, ships and any other weather conditions.

The fundamental principle underpinning radar operation revolves around the transmission of electromagnetic waves, typically in the microwave or radio frequency bands, from a transmitter towards a target area. Upon encountering objects within this area, a portion of the transmitted energy is reflected towards the radar receiver. By analyzing the properties of these reflected signals, such as their amplitude, frequency, and time delay, radar systems can discern valuable information about the detected objects, including their distance, velocity, size, and composition. The need for radar technology stems from its unique ability to operate effectively in adverse weather conditions and low visibility scenarios, where other sensing modalities may falter. Radar systems offer round-the-clock surveillance capabilities, capable of monitoring vast areas with high precision and accuracy. Moreover, radar enables non-intrusive detection, allowing for covert surveillance without direct line-of-sight access to the target.

Various types of radar include surveillance radar, weather radar, synthetic aperture radar (SAR), and airborne early warning radar, among others. The choice of radar type depends on factors such as mission objectives, range, resolution, and platform constraints. Modern fighter jets leverage airborne radar technology as a critical sensor for achieving air superiority. These advanced systems employ radio waves to generate a detailed picture of the surrounding airspace, enabling superior detection and tracking of other aircraft even in limited visibility conditions. This translates to a tactical advantage in air-to-air combat, as pilots can precisely pinpoint enemy locations, determine their range and size, and effectively guide missiles for engagements. Furthermore, airborne radar serves a dual role by providing vital navigational data, constantly scanning for obstacles to ensure the safe operation of the fighter jet. Notably, advancements in radar technology have led to the integration of Active Electronically Scanned Array (AESA) systems in modern fighter jets. AESA technology offers significant improvements in target detection capabilities and resistance to jamming attempts, making these fighter jets even more formidable in any aerial confrontation.

The scanning mechanism of airborne radar antennas, constrained within a range of ± 60 degrees in both azimuth and elevation, presents a significant challenge for fighter aircraft operations. This mechanical limitation inevitably results in blind spots within the pilot's field of view, compromising the radar's surveillance capabilities. Consequently, the aircraft becomes vulnerable to potential threats, as it may unknowingly enter the enemy's firing range without detection. This predicament exacerbates the difficulty for pilots in effectively countering incoming threats, thereby increasing the likelihood of being engaged by hostile forces. The restricted scanning range not only undermines situational awareness but also hampers the aircraft's overall combat effectiveness, highlighting the critical need for technological advancements to address these operational limitations and enhance survivability in hostile environments.

Niraj Prasad Bhatta et.al. [1] has investigated the fundamentals, practical mechanics, and uses of radar technology in air traffic control, surveillance, meteorological monitoring, and disaster relief. They emphasize how important it is to safety and security, emphasizing the necessity of high-power transmission and thorough target data. In order to achieve the high accuracy

tracking result and fast response demand for MAB system, the antenna tracking platform is designed with proper gear mechanism and control method [2]. Steering mounting systems for high gain airborne satellite antennas requires precise alignment despite aircraft movements [3]. Gimbal design for antenna and radome measurements requires drive encoder setup with high accuracy precise positioning in aircraft web applications [4]. Active gimbal system for small RPAs in improving real-time video transmission quality and range requires the use advanced technologies like OFDM, active faced array antenna, MIMO topology, and satellite repeater technology considering weight constraints, power consumption and promising results [5]. High precision servo control system for single gimbal control movement gyroscope (SGCMG) can be used to improve angular speed accuracy due to nonlinear friction disturbances and coupling torque and this system uses a nonlinear cascade extended state observer, enhancing gimbal system performance [6]. In stabilizing gimbal platform, focusing on friction resonance and vibration's impact on line-of-sight stability depends on gyro selection and control strategies, despite being limited to a specific 2DOF ISG design and relying on simulations [7]. For validating the performance of parallel airborne SAR antenna stabilized platform using the 3-UPS/S mechanism done using mathematical equations through co-simulation and physical experiments by demonstrating the three DOF mechanism's accuracy [8]. The performance of the metamaterial absorber was evaluated through simulations using CST software, with polarization angles ranging from 0 degree to 80 degrees and maximize the absorption of radar waves in the X-band frequency [9]. Use of servo motor controller for antenna stabilization using a proportional integral derivative control system show satisfactory performance, negligible steady state errors, and good alignment between servo motor angle and imu sensor data and this controller is suitable for dynamic fields like shift vehicles and military vehicles [10]. Antenna Control Servo System (ACSS) designed for Doppler weather radar using direct drive motors to overcome geared system limitations like noise and high maintenance costs and this system has increased efficiency, reduced noise, longer lifetime, high torque, and fast positioning [11]. The helical antennas are categorized into two modes, normal and axial mode and the axial mode has better directional characteristic [12].

2. CAD Model of Wedge Mechanism

The paper presents a specially designed mechanism to pivot the radar. It incorporates principles taken from the swash plate mechanism used in a helicopter to pivot rotor blades. Autodesk Fusion CAD software is primarily used to design the realistic model of the mechanism and for further refinement SolidWorks software is used for the analysis model. The main function of this mechanism is to convert a rotary motion into a pivoting action which helps the radar complete its ± 105 degrees of azimuth and elevation. This newly designed mechanism solves all the mentioned problems very effectively compared to the existing mechanisms incorporated in the current fighter jets.

The designed mechanism enables the radar to scan a wider range eliminating a major portion of the blind spot, which increases the overall awareness and fighting capabilities of the fighter jet. New airborne radar systems in fighter jets are a game-changer. This system is compact, saving space for other equipment, and their simplified design means easier maintenance. Built for durability to handle harsh environments, these cost-effective radars offer superior capabilities at a better price. This translates to a significant advantage for fighter jets, keeping them on top in the aerial arena. The 3D drawing of wedge mechanism is shown in Figure 1. The important parts of wedge mechanism include shell, slew ring, universal joint, NEMA34 stepper motor, worm and ring gears. The shell of fighter jet radars rely on a lightweight, aerospace-grade aluminium shell (aluminium 6061-T6) for its strength and minimal weight. This critical component is housed within a radar mount that acts as both a sturdy base and a precise aiming mechanism, handling external pressure while allowing for specific swivel angles.

Figure.1. 3D drawing of wedge mechanism

Fighter jet radars are marvels of rotating precision. An electrical signal instructs the motor to spin at a specific speed, which is then translated by a worm gear into the rotation of the radar's shell and ring gear. The sturdy lower slew ring supports this movement, while the upper slew ring allows the antenna to pivot at a 45-degree angle within the shell. To ensure the antenna's face stays stable during this process, a universal joint cancels out any wobbles, enabling smooth and precise scanning across a wide range of elevations and azimuths (up to +/- 105 degrees).

3. Finite Element Analysis

According to the environmental test conditions, the modal analysis, static structural, random vibration and shock response analysis of the model were carried out. Figure 2 and Figure 3 shows the mesh generation result of the wedge mechanism with and without shell respectively. The whole model is meshed by the method of body sizing. The accuracy and speed of operation are considered to increase the rationality of mesh generation. The whole model is divided into 1937727 nodes and 1048602 elements were generated. The Shell is made up of Aluminium 6061-T6 and the rest of the parts are made up of Structural Steel.

Figure.2. Mesh generation for wedge mechanism with Shell

Figure.3. Mesh generation for wedge mechanism without Shell

For all the analysis conducted, the base plate has been given as the fixed support and a distributed mass of 150 kg is specified for the top dummy plate. The constraints (fixed support) and distributed mass considered for the analysis is as shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5 respectively. The total deformation and equivalent stress were determined for all the tests except for modal analysis.

Figure.4. Fixed support for all the tests

Figure.5. Distributed mass

Modal analysis is used to determine the vibration characteristics of the design structure or mechanical components. They are important parameters in the structural design under dynamic loads and are the basis for more detailed dynamic analysis. Using Lanczos method, the analysis is carried out after setting the constraints in ANSYS. According to the relevant vibration theory, the influence of the low-order mode of the structure on the vibration response is relatively large, and the influence of the high-order mode can be ignored. Figure 6 & Figure 7 shows the graph and table of first ten natural frequencies obtained from modal analysis respectively. Mass participation factor specifies the percentage of how much the structural mass of the model is participating for a given direction and mode. Mass participation factor should be more than 85% for accurate dynamic results.

Figure.6. Graph of modal analysis

Tabular Data		
	Mode	Frequency [Hz]
1	1.	256.56
2	2.	272.88
3	3.	471.45
4	4.	607.84
5	5.	646.
6	6.	817.15
7	7.	961.89
8	8.	1088.3
9	9.	1120.5
10	10.	1133.

Figure.7. Data of modal frequency

A static structural analysis determines the effect of steady (or static) loading conditions on a structure, while omitting inertia and damping effects, such as those caused by time varying loads. Static structural measurements is the most common analysis performed for verification and/or validation, but does not indicate that they are always simple in nature. Boundary conditions for Static Structural analysis considered is standard Earth gravity which is equal to 9.81 m/s^2 .

Shock loading refers to a sudden, forceful application of a load that creates a high-intensity, short-duration impact on a structure. Examples include explosions, collisions, or earthquakes. The boundary conditions for shock operational are shock time is set as 11ms and the acceleration given is 15g. The obtained half sine wave shock pulse operational is shown in Figure 8.

Figure.8. Half sine wave shock pulse operational

Random vibration analysis is a powerful tool for simulating how a structure responds to vibrations that are unpredictable and constantly changing in frequency and magnitude. It's ideal for analyzing components subjected to real-world scenarios with fluctuating vibrations, unlike the steady loads used in static analysis. Random vibration testing uses the power spectral density (PSD) for test development and data analysis. The PSD graph displays resonances and harmonics that are hidden in a time-history waveform. In practice, generating a PSD is often the first step in examining and analyzing a random waveform. The PSD G acceleration is applied in the X direction. The PSD G acceleration graph and the acceleration values for the random vibrations is 0 to 2000 Hz are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10 respectively.

Figure.9. PSD G acceleration graph

Tabular Data		
	Frequency [Hz]	☒ G Acceleration [G ² /Hz]
1	20.	1.e-002
2	80.	4.e-002
3	350.	4.e-002
4	2000.	8.e-003
*		

Figure.10. PSD G acceleration values

4. Result and discussion

The mechanism designed has effectively achieved a movement range from ± 60 to ± 105 degrees in both azimuth and elevation. The field of view has been increased with notable decrease in blind spot from 67% to 42%, enhancing overall situational awareness and minimizing potential vulnerabilities. Achieves desired range within 2 seconds using high-performance components and low-friction design. Lowers power consumption below 300 watts through efficient motor selection and lightweight build, the mechanism has achieved to fit within 400 mm from the given constraint of 500 mm height, while adhering to the radar's size & weight constraint. The following FEA results were obtained for the different tests conducted.

From the result shown in Figure 11 the mass participation factors have been obtained. The mass participation factors during translation are found to be 0.90738 or 90.738% in X-direction, 0.8955 or 89.55% in Y-direction and 0.87565 or 87.565% in Z-direction. The mass participation factors during rotation are found to be 0.62629 or 62.629% in X-direction, 0.69572 or 69.572% in Y-direction and 0.83994 or 83.994% in Z-direction.

Mode	Frequency [Hz]	X Direction	Y Direction	Z Direction	Rotation X	Rotation Y	Rotation Z
1	256.56	0.86629	5.6611e-010	7.0489e-003	2.2165e-008	0.42365	1.1627e-005
2	272.88	1.3777e-008	0.88443	8.4932e-007	0.49451	3.4349e-008	2.7334e-002
3	471.45	2.1903e-002	6.4436e-007	0.3613	4.2881e-006	0.14826	1.2986e-007
4	607.84	1.0273e-006	8.8436e-004	2.6454e-007	4.2666e-002	2.3435e-005	0.15531
5	646.	9.1776e-003	8.5441e-008	0.14871	2.1872e-006	5.3831e-002	3.1056e-005
6	817.15	6.6499e-003	2.6183e-007	0.35309	3.9064e-006	3.1079e-002	5.453e-006
7	961.89	1.163e-007	1.3564e-002	1.4619e-007	8.9037e-002	4.9866e-008	0.65642
8	1088.3	1.0654e-004	1.5518e-006	5.4955e-003	1.746e-005	1.2338e-002	3.927e-006
9	1120.5	2.7488e-007	6.6105e-004	1.3651e-008	4.3008e-005	4.68e-007	8.1872e-004
10	1133.	3.2549e-003	7.7221e-010	1.5202e-005	1.514e-006	2.6535e-002	1.1648e-008
Sum		0.90738	0.89955	0.87565	0.62629	0.69572	0.83994

Figure.11. Model analysis result

The result of static structural analysis shown in Table1, Figure 12, Figure 13, Figure 14 and Figure 15 shows the deformation and equivalent stress when static structural load applied on mechanism without shell and with shell. From Table 1, it can be seen that the maximum stress is acting on the universal joint which is much lesser than the yield stress of 250 MPa for structural steel.

Figure.12. Deformation of mechanism without shell under static structural load

Figure.13. Deformation of mechanism with shell under static structural load

Figure.14. Equivalent (von-mises) stress developed in mechanism without shell under static structural load

Figure.15. Equivalent (von-mises) stress developed in mechanism with shell under static structural load

Table.1. Result of static structural analysis of wedge mechanism

Sl. No	Particulars	Minimum	Maximum	Average
1	Total Deformation (mm)	0	4.6607×10^{-3}	1.8573×10^{-3}
2	Equivalent stress (MPa)	2.1619×10^{-4}	3.4254	0.27839

Figure 16, Figure 17, Figure 18 and Figure 19 shows the deformation of mechanism and distribution of equivalent stress on the mechanism without shell and with shell during shock operational test. Figure 20 and Figure 21 shows the time history plots of deformation and equivalent stress of mechanism during shock operational test. From Table 2, it can be seen that the maximum stress is acting on the universal joint which is much lesser than the yield stress of 250 MPa for structural steel.

Figure.16. Deformation of mechanism without shell under shock operational test

Figure.17. Deformation of mechanism with shell under shock operational test

Figure.18. Equivalent (von-mises) stress developed in mechanism without shell during shock operational test

Figure.19. Equivalent (von-mises) stress developed in mechanism with shell during shock operational test

Figure.20. Time history of deformation of mechanism under shock operational test

Figure.21. Time history of equivalent stress under shock operational test of mechanism

Table.2. Result table for shock operational of wedge mechanism

Sl. No	Particulars	Minimum	Maximum	Average
1	Total Deformation (mm)	0	1.8056×10^{-3}	6.1724×10^{-4}
2	Equivalent stress (MPa)	4.0165×10^{-3}	55.51	4.4191

Figure 22, Figure 23, Figure 24 and Figure 25 show the directional deformation of mechanism and distribution of equivalent stress in the mechanism without shell and with shell during random vibration test. From Table 3, it can be seen that the maximum stress is acting on the universal joint which is lesser than the yield stress of 250MPa for structural steel.

Figure.22. Directional deformation of mechanism without shell under random vibration test

Figure.23. Directional deformation of mechanism with shell under random vibration test

Figure.24. Distribution of equivalent stress in the mechanism without shell under random vibration test

Figure.25. Distribution of equivalent stress in the mechanism with shell under random vibration test

Table.3. Result of random vibration analysis of mechanism

Sl. No	Particulars	Minimum	Maximum	Average
1	Directional Deformation(mm)	0	0.24258	8.3672×10^{-2}
2	Equivalent Stress(MPa)	1.7015×10^{-2}	222.9	14.28

5. Conclusion

This research work aimed at solving the problem with fighter jet radars. The radars could only see only a limited area, leaving blind spots where enemies could hide. Hence, a new mechanism was designed for the radar that allows it to move more, like a wider searchlight. With the new mechanism attachment the radar can see much further, reducing blind spots and making it harder for enemies to surprise the pilot. Also attempt made to ensure that the mechanism designed fits inside the jet's radome and is also power efficient. With significant modification in the design can significantly improve the fighter jet's scanning capability, making safer and more effective in combat. The result obtained are satisfactory and deformation of mechanism and equivalent stress in mechanism are within limits under modal analysis, static structural, shock operational and random vibration analysis tests.

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